

THE MICROMECHANICS OF FRACTURE

IN FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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1. SYMBOLS

GRP	Glass reinforced (thermosetting) plastic
CFRP	Carbon fibre reinforced (thermosetting) plastic
F RTP	Fibre reinforced thermoplastic
L_c	Critical fibre length at fracture
E_f	Youngs modulus of fibre
σ_{uf}	Fibre fracture stress
τ_{mf}	Shear strength of fibre/matrix interface
r_f	fibre radius
ϵ_c^u	ultimate composite strain
ϵ_m^u	strain in matrix at composite failure
ϵ_f^u	strain in fibre at composite failure

2. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of most thermoplastic materials may be usefully enhanced by the incorporation of suitable filler materials. These are usually inorganic particulate or fibrous substances such as talc, asbestos, glass ballotini and both glass and carbon fibres. The general effect of the particulate fillers is to improve the low strain modulus, raise the heat distortion temperature and improve the dimensional stability of the thermoplastic. The fibrous fillers additionally offer the possibility of much greater modulus and strength enhancement.

The constitution of fibre-reinforced thermoplastics (F RTP)

differs in three important aspects from that of the more conventional glass and fibre reinforced thermosetting resin materials (GRP and CFRP). Firstly in order that the reinforced thermoplastic may be processed by the conventional route for that material, principally by injection moulding (and this is possibly the most important attraction of the material), it is necessary that the fibres are in discrete short lengths rather than as continuous filaments. The same requirements of mouldability also limits the maximum proportion of fibres which may be utilised. This upper limit is dependent on the length of the fibres but is close to a V_f of 0.4 in most cases. The final point concerns the fibre orientation and distribution. In GRP and CFRP the fibres, in the form of rovings, cloths, mats or felts, are placed more or less precisely where required; whereas in FRTP the fibre distribution is complex and depends on the flow pattern generated during the moulding operation which is in turn influenced by both the mould and runner design, and by the machine settings (e.g. temperature, injection rate etc). The fibre length distribution is influenced by both the material compounding and the moulding operations (1).

The extent to which these short, misaligned fibres enhance the stiffness and strength of the composite depends on their relative volume fraction, their length, their orientation and the shear strength of the bond between the fibre and the thermoplastic matrix. The concept of a critical fibre length, L_c , is well established (2), but it is usually applied to the case of fibre fracture. Thus an aligned fibre of length L_c represents the shortest fibre which may be loaded up to its L_c fracture stress by shear transfer from the matrix;

when:
$$L_c = \frac{\sigma_{uf} r}{\tau_{mf}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

and fibres of length greater than L_c would fracture when the strain in the composite, ϵ_c , exceeded the L_c fibre strain to fracture.

$$\epsilon_c > \frac{\sigma_f^u}{E_f} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

However, even at levels of strain below that necessary for fibre fracture, the stiffness enhancement is subject to a similar critical fibre length effect (3) which at any value of composite strain is given by:

$$L_\epsilon = \frac{E_f \epsilon_c r}{\tau_{mf}} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Fibres of this critical length will be strained to the same value as the matrix at their centre point. Those which are shorter will be strained to a lesser extent, and thus carry less load; whilst longer fibres will have a region of length $L - L_\epsilon$ in their centres which will be strained uniformly with the matrix. In terms of reinforcement efficiency an infinite fibre would give a value of 1

(i.e. as predicted by the simple law of mixtures equation), a fibre of the critical length would give a value of only 0.5, but at $5 L_c$ the efficiency rises to 0.9. At low strains L_c will be very small but will rise as the strain increases, up to ϵ_c the value L_c when fibre fracture would occur. So that in a composite containing fibres of a range of lengths, at small strains all the fibres will be of length greater than L_c and the stiffness enhancement will be high but as the strain increases the shorter fibres will be progressively unable to carry such a high proportion of the total load, so that the apparent stiffness enhancement efficiency will drop. The enhancement efficiency will also be reduced by any misalignment of the fibres relative to the direction of loading. Thus in order to predict the stiffness of a FRTP it would be necessary to measure the total fibre length distribution and the relative fibre orientation and to measure the effective strength of the fibre/matrix interface τ_{mf} . In an attempt to do this, Bowyer and Bader (3, 4, 5) estimated that the value of L_c at 0.02 strain for 12 μm diameter E-glass fibres in nylon 6.6 was approximately 0.2 mm and 0.12 mm for 8 μm diameter H.S. type carbon fibres. Optimum efficiency would thus be achieved with lengths exceeding about 1 mm; this was an order of magnitude greater than the lengths found in currently available commercial materials. The estimated values for τ_{mf} were 45 MN/m^2 for the nylon/glass and $\sim 130 \text{ MN/m}^2$ for the nylon/carbon interface. This latter value is greater than the shear strength of the matrix - a point which will be discussed later. The orientation effect was allowed for by a simple factor C. This would be 1.0 for perfect alignment, 0.33 for random fibres in one plane, and 0.167 for a completely three dimensional random distribution. The values measured varied over the range 0.7 to 0.33 for various fibre/matrix combinations in injection moulded tensile test pieces. In the case of materials having relatively long fibres, the orientation factor was generally greater than 0.55, indicating a substantial degree of alignment.

The implication of this work was that the ideal FRTP should contain as high as practicable a volume fraction of fibres, of length exceeding $5 L_c$ (i.e. $> 1 \text{ mm}$). These were manufactured and the mechanical test programme revealed materials of outstanding stiffness and excellent strength. The strength enhancement was however much less than that of stiffness, due to the fact that fracture occurred at lower values of strain when high volume fractions of relatively long fibres were used. This is clearly illustrated in Figures 1, 2 and 3.

The actual strain at fracture of the more highly filled composites is somewhat less than that of the fibres in single fibre tensile tests. This might suggest that the strength of the fibres is reduced significantly during the compounding and moulding operations, but that failure of the composite is initiated by the fracture of fibres of length greater than L_c . An alternative hypothesis is that fracture is initiated in the matrix due to the

stress concentrating effect of the fibres and that the strain never reaches the critical level to cause fibre fracture.

In the present work we have sought to explain this embrittlement by a more extensive study of the mechanical properties of glass and carbon fibre reinforced nylon and polypropylene and by concurrent studies of the mechanism of failure in both FRTP and model systems.

3. MATERIALS

The principal materials used in the investigation have been nylon 6.6 and polypropylene, which have been reinforced with either E-glass or HS (high strength) carbon fibres. The nylon was 'Maranyl A 100' supplied by ICI Plastics Ltd and the polypropylenes designated 'Propathene PXC 8639' also supplied by ICI. The 'Propathene' is a special compound designed to 'couple' with a suitable surface finished glass fibre to produce a strong interfacial bond. The glass fibre rovings were supplied by Fibreglass Ltd. a grade designated FGRE1 treated with a size, MSS 1421, being used with the nylon and FGRE 5 with size MSS 301 for the polypropylene, these sizes being designed to be compatible with the respective polymers. The carbon fibre used was 'Modmor Type II-S' a high strength surface treated fibre prepared from a polyacrylonitrile precursor by Morganite Modmor Ltd. A moulding compound was prepared by extrusion coating the fibre roving with the appropriate polymer, and then chopping to give pellets of a size suitable for injection moulding. The process is described in more detail in reference (1). These pellets were then injection moulded into suitable test pieces using a screw preplasticising moulding machine. The tensile test piece had a gauge portion 40 mm long and 5 mm x 2 mm cross-section. The isochronous and elevated temperature data was obtained with an ICI type creep test piece 100 mm long and of 6 mm x 2 mm cross section. Both these test pieces were moulded simultaneously in a multicavity mould.

Moulding conditions had to be varied according to the fibre content but care was taken to avoid overheating and degradation of the polymer due to long residence times in the plasticising section of the moulding machine. All test pieces tested were taken from the middle group of long moulding runs. This ensured good repeatability between tests. The test pieces were conditioned by holding in a room maintained at 20°C and approximately 50% relative humidity for a period of at least 28 days prior to testing.

Model composites were also made using similar fibres but in transparent polyester resin and polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) matrices to allow optical observation of the failure processes. These model composites were made up with relatively low volume fractions of fibres, both continuous and short fibres were used and samples of various controlled distributions were prepared. The fibre was incorporated in the liquid resin, taking care to prevent any preferential fibre orientation, in a suitable mould and was then cured at room temperature using a conventional initiator

and accelerator in the case of polyester and an ultra-violet light curing initiator (benzoin) in the case of the methylmethacrylate monomer.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

4.1 Mechanical testing: Tensile tests on the moulded composite test pieces were carried out on an Instron testing machine using an Instron strain gauge extensometer to measure the strain. Force and strain were recorded against time on a two-pen recorder incorporated in the testing machine. The elevated and sub-zero temperature tests were conducted on the same machine but using an air circulating, controlled environment cabinet. Heat was by a conventional electric heating element and cooling by a controlled supply of liquid nitrogen.

The short term creep tests for determining the isochronous strength data were carried out on a modified, dead weight loading, metal creep testing machine. A similar controlled environment cabinet was used, but the strain was measured by means of an LVDT (microformer) extensometer.

4.2 Materials Characterisation: The principal objective of this characterisation was to determine the total fibre content, V_f , and the length range of the fibres in the moulded test pieces. The V_f was determined in the case of glass fibre filled materials by heating a weighed sample taken from the test piece (about 0.5 g) at 600°C in air, then weighing the residual fibres after all the polymer had burnt off. This was a very reliable method, but it could not be used for the carbon fibre containing samples. In those with the nylon matrix, a sample was digested in a concentrated sulphuric acid/hydrogen peroxide mixture (6) and the residual fibres then filtered off and weighed. Unfortunately this method was not satisfactory for the polypropylene based materials which had to be dissolved in hot 'Dekalin', when the fibres could again be filtered off and weighed. This was, however, the least satisfactory of the methods used.

The fibre length distribution was determined by taking a small sample, burning off or digesting to release the fibres as described above and then spreading a representative sample on a microscope slide. This was photographed with a reference graticule and from a suitable print, the individual fibres could then be counted and measured. Much of this work was done manually but a Zeiss particle size analyser was available during one stage of the work, which considerably eased the tedium of this particular operation.

4.3 Microscopy and Fractography: In parallel with the mechanical testing, a programme of optical microscopy on polished sections cut from the test pieces and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the fracture surfaces was conducted. This, however, did not provide information sought as to whether the failure was initiated by individual fibre fracture or by matrix failure due to the stress

concentrating effect of the fibres. Accordingly some fracture experiments were carried out on transparent composites containing small quantities of fibrous fillers. The object was to view the failure process under the optical microscope and to identify the relevant micro-failure mechanisms. The systems selected were an unsaturated polyester resin with E-glass and polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) also with E-glass fibre. These systems provide a good optical match between the fibre and the matrix so that the fibre can be observed without excessive optical reflection or scattering at the fibre/matrix interface. Various test piece designs were evaluated, the most successful being a miniature version of the double cantilever cleavage fracture of the form described by Berry (7). This was mounted on a simple rig with a micrometer straining mechanism, which could be mounted on the stage of a Zeiss Ultraphot microscope, and the straining mechanism operated whilst the specimen was viewed through the microscope. In order to overcome the difficulties imposed by the limited depth of focus at higher magnifications ($\sim 400\times$), the specimen was made in the form of an asymmetric sandwich. This is shown in Figure 4. First a thick, ~ 4 mm, layer of unfilled matrix was cast; when this had partially cured a thin layer, $\sim 1 - 2$ mm, of the filled material was cast on to it, to be followed in due course by a third thin layer of the unfilled matrix material. The composite sheet was then machined flat and polished and the test piece cut out of it. Then crack restraining grooves were cut from either face into the central filled region. The specimen was then set up on the microscope so that it was viewed through the thin clear layer whilst illuminated from below. In this way it was possible to follow the progress of the crack tip as the specimen was opened. Some specimens without side notches were also tested, since the notches tended to partially obscure the crack from view. In practice it was then difficult to predict the crack path and the amount of opening action necessary to maintain stable crack growth. However, it did prove possible to follow cracks for several millimeters of growth and to observe both the fibre/crack interaction and the behaviour of fibres and interfaces in the regions close to the crack. Specimens were prepared with short random fibres and also with single filaments placed at predetermined intervals and angles relative to the crack path.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Mechanical Properties: Tensile tests and short term creep tests were conducted over the temperature range -60 to $+80$ degrees C. on a batch of each of the glass and carbon fibre filled nylon 6.6 and polypropylene composites. The volume fraction of fibres was close to 0.2 for all the materials. These were processed to give relatively long fibre lengths, and the actual values measured are given in Table 1.

The fibre length distribution quoted is based on the total volume fraction of fibres (V_f) in the sample (in this case 0.2), thus 10 volume % of the fibres measured (i.e. $0.02 V_f$) were shorter

TABLE 1

Material	Fibre length Distribution			Calculated critical length L_c at $\epsilon = .01$ (mm)	Median aspect ratio
	10 percentile length (mm)	Median length (mm)	90 percentile length (mm)		
Nylon 6.6/E glass	0.28	0.58	1.25	0.1	48
Nylon 6.6/Carbon	0.14	0.32	0.73	0.07	40
Polypropylene/E glass	0.40	0.95	3.4	0.16	79
Polypropylene/Carbon	0.20	0.55	2.9	0.30	69

than the 10 percentile length and 10 volume % were larger than the 90 percentile length. The critical length calculated is the value at a strain of 0.01 using the values of τ_{mf} calculated from test data at 20°C (4,5). It will be noted that with the exception of carbon/polypropylene, the 10 percentile length is greater than L_c and the median length is approximately 5 L_c . L_c for the polypropylene/carbon is relatively longer, because the value of τ_{mf} was very low for this material. Hence, although the actual fibre lengths are longer than those in the nylon/carbon system, they are less effective.

It should be noted that L_c is directly proportional to strain (equation 3), and thus a considerable proportion of the fibres in all the materials would remain supercritical to the fibre fracture strain (~ 0.015 for carbon and ~ 0.035 for glass).

The results of the tensile tests are summarised in Figures 5 to 10, which show the variation of stiffness, strength and ductility with temperature for the four materials. In all materials both stiffness and strength fall quite sharply as the temperature is raised, but the strain at fracture shows only a gradual increase with temperature. At 60°C the stiffness of the polypropylene/carbon has fallen to half the value at 0°C, and its strength likewise, but the strain to fracture increases only from 0.01 to 0.011.

The effective degree of reinforcement may be expressed as the ratio of the property of the composite with that of the unfilled polymer under similar conditions. Expressed in this way the ratio is remarkably constant for maximum strength for each material, over the temperature range investigated; but the stiffness reinforcement increases at the higher temperature as shown in Table 2.

It will be noted that the nylon composites show

TABLE 2.

Material	Strength ratios ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)					Stiffness ratios ($\epsilon = 0.005$) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)				
	-40	-20	0	20	40	-40	-20	0	20	40
Polypropylene/Glass	1.6	1.8	2.0	2.3	2.5	1.4	1.9	2.4	3.1	4.0
Polypropylene/Carbon	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.3	2.0	2.1	2.5	3.0	3.6	4.0
Nylon/Glass	2.5	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.8	5.0	6.4	7.5	8.3	10
Nylon/Carbon	3.7	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.1	8.0	9.9	11	12	14

relatively superior ratios and the carbon is generally more effective than the glass, except in the case of the polypropylene/carbon at high temperatures. The very high ratios for the stiffness reinforcement of the nylons should be treated with caution, however, as they may be influenced by the moisture content of the nylon. The nylons were equilibrated at about 50% relative humidity and it is known that dry-unfilled material would be twice as stiff, but the full effects of moisture content in the filled materials have not been evaluated.

The isochronous stress strain curves at 20°C and 50°C for the nylon composites are shown in figures 11 and 12. These show a small viscoelastic effect at the lower but, as expected, greater effects at the higher temperatures. A similar trend was observed in the polypropylene based composites. The effectiveness of the reinforcement appears to be comparable for both the 10 s. and 1000 s. values at 20°C , but the glass filled materials appear to be marginally more effective in retaining their resistance to deformation at 50°C and 1000 s.

The implication of these results is that all the materials are effectively stiffened at 20°C and that the nylon/carbon combination is the most effective. At low strains the fibre length distribution was such that with the exception of the polypropylene/carbon, over half the fibre content was of length exceeding $5 L_c$. The ultimate strength enhancement was limited in all the materials by their low ductility, and at 20°C the relative short fibre length of the polypropylene/carbon showed no deleterious effect.

The fall off in stiffness at elevated temperatures is much greater than would be predicted by applying the reduction in matrix stiffness to the law of mixtures equation (the fibre stiffness would not vary significantly over the temperature range investigated). The reduction in stiffness must therefore be attributed to a change in the matrix/fibre interaction. If the matrix shear modulus and strength is reduced by a similar proportion to its tensile properties, the effective value of the interface strength τ_{mf} must be reduced. At ambient temperatures the estimates of τ_{mf} have been of the same order as the matrix shear strength, but it is possible that at elevated temperatures it could fall to lower relative values due to the effects of differential thermal expansion between matrix and fibre. This will tend to decrease any frictional component of τ_{mf} , and will have the effect of increasing the value of

L_c and L_e , so that a fibre of effective length at 20°C would be less so at a higher temperature. It will be noted that the two carbon filled materials, although stiffer than the glass filled equivalents, show a greater proportionate reduction in stiffness at the higher temperatures. This is especially noticeable in the polypropylene/carbon, which has the least favourable fibre length distribution. This emphasizes the need to ensure both good interface strength and adequate fibre length for effective reinforcement.

The maximum strength of all the materials appears to be limited by their ductility, as the strain at fracture does not increase as the stiffness is reduced at higher temperatures. The level of this fracture strain is 0.015 - 0.022 for the glass and 0.007 - 0.015 for the carbon. The lowest values were obtained with the nylon matrix in each case (these systems having the highest τ_{mf} values). Earlier work (3, 4, and Fig.3) had indicated that as V_f^{mf} was increased, the fracture strain decreased to the level observed in the present work. The actual level of strain is rather lower than might be expected to cause fibre fracture but the fibre obviously has some influence as evidenced by the much lower ductility of the carbon filled materials. All the materials tested contained a significant proportion of very long fibres (i.e. over 10 L_c) and it might be expected that fracture be initiated by failures in these long fibres which might remain supercritical even at the higher temperatures. The relatively low strain in comparison with the expected strain to cause fibre failure could be explained by fibre misalignment, and fibre damage induced during the compounding and moulding operation (see Fig. 13). An attempt was made to establish whether extensive fibre fracture did occur. Samples were taken from broken test pieces from next to the fracture site, the matrix burnt off or digested by chemical means to release the fibres, and the fibre length distribution determined. It was considered that if a significant amount of fibre fracture occurred during failure, then a reduction in the quantity of long fibres would be observed. This was not the case, although it must be conceded that the sensitivity of the experiment was open to question. This leads to the conclusion that the fracture is initiated either in the matrix, or more probably at the fibre/matrix interface where large stress concentrations must exist. This view was confirmed by microscopic examination of sections cut through failed test pieces, which showed extensive cracking, Figure 13, and by the SEM examination which showed the brittle nature of the matrix failure. This is discussed more fully in a later section.

5.2 Fractography: Figure 14 is a typical SEM photomicrograph of a room temperature tensile fracture in the nylon/glass material. The matrix appears to fail in an essentially brittle manner and extensive fibre pull out is seen. The maximum pull out length observed was about 250 μm (20 diameters) which is the median half length. There is no significant difference between carbon and glass filled materials at 20°C. At the sub zero temperatures the failure is generally similar (Fig.15) but the pull out length is rather less

(10 - 15 diameters) and at the higher temperatures, evidence of matrix flow is observed (Fig.16). In these high temperature fractures the pull out length is greater than at room temperature (but more difficult to measure accurately) and there is less evidence of misaligned fibres. It is possible that they become aligned during the failure process. It is interesting to note that this clear visual evidence of microscopic ductility is not reflected in the overall strain to fracture recorded in the tensile tests. The polypropylene composites show evidence of matrix flow at 20°C (Fig.17) but also appear to be brittle at -70°C (Fig.18). There is evidence of good adhesion between matrix and fibre in the nylon composites (Figs. 19 and 20) but the polypropylene composites show cleaner fibre surfaces suggesting less adhesion (Fig. 17).

A limited number of tests were conducted on wet nylon composites (soaked in water at 20°C for 28 days). These show fracture characteristics similar to those for the dryer material at higher temperatures. Figure 21 is a photograph of a wet nylon/carbon specimen fractured at 20°C. In addition to the matrix flow, the spread of the fracture from a fibre end (or possibly a fibre fracture) is clearly visible. The gross ductility of this test piece was somewhat higher than that of the dryer material.

This fractographic evidence confirms the general failure hypothesis that the matrix behaves in a brittle manner, at lower temperatures and that even some marked evidence of matrix flow at elevated temperatures does not confer general macroscopic ductility to the material. The pull out lengths observed suggest that, except at the lowest temperatures, fibres are pulling out rather than breaking within the matrix. There is also limited evidence that fibre ends might act as crack starters.

6. FRACTURE OF MODEL COMPOSITES

Although scanning electron microscopy of the fractured test pieces can yield valuable data such as fibre pull out lengths and orientations (Figs. 14 to 21), it yields very limited information of the fracture mechanism itself. The model system studied was designed to allow direct optical observation of the fracture mechanism. The model must be chosen to be as like the real system as possible, so that analogies between the behaviour in the real and model systems can be drawn. To obtain maximum optical transparency in the model, E glass fibre was used, in low volume fractions (0.01). The fibre was chopped into short lengths of the same order as the real system, some surface treated, some with the surface sizing burnt off. In later batches of specimens, glass fibre burnt off from glass/polypropylene mouldings was used, thus retaining the same range of fibre lengths in the model system as in the reinforced thermoplastics.

Choice of the matrix is more difficult, since several of the conditions which ought to be fulfilled, conflict. The real thermoplastic matrices are semi-crystalline, and thus opaque, but for the

model system to be transparent, the matrix must be amorphous, and so differ from the real system. However, since a comparison of the macroscopic properties of filled crystalline polymers and filled amorphous polymers (such as glass reinforced polyesters) can be made, it is not unreasonable to compare the microscopic properties; and at least, the interaction of cracks with short fibres is unlikely to be much affected by bulk matrix variations.

To permit observation of fracture in the model system by transmission optical microscopy, the refractive indices of the fibre and matrix must be closely matched to minimise internal reflection at the fibre/matrix interface, and so render the system as transparent as possible. The fracture strains of the model and real matrices must also be similar. Dried nylon does not cold draw at room temperature, and fails at a strain of about 0.06, but work has shown that nylon moulded at the slightly elevated temperatures required to mould filled thermoplastics, will fail at slightly lower strains. Three model matrices have been investigated, the choice being reached by a compromise; Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), an unsaturated polyester resin (clear casting), and a flexibilised polyester resin. The fracture strain of polyester is low, less than the fibre, so the PMMA is probably a better choice of model matrix having a higher failure strain and the additional advantage that a more controlled fracture can be obtained.

The model system shows all the normal features associated with fracture in fibre reinforced composite materials. Fibre pull out is frequently observed, and fibres can be watched as they pull out and leave sockets in the matrix (Fig.22). PMMA models show less pull out than polyester matrices, due to the increased fibre/matrix bond strength. Fibres that lie more than a few degrees from the perpendicular to the crack do not pull out at all, and break in the plane of the crack. They do, however, debond to the same order of distance from the crack as fibres perpendicular to the crack (which is often considerably larger than pull out lengths of fibres lying perpendicular to the crack). These fibres will thus contribute less to the fracture toughness of the material.

Crack blunting by fibre debonding is visible, in the classic Cook and Gordon mechanism (8), where a weak interface lying perpendicular to the crack path is opened up by the triaxial stress system at the crack tip, effectively blunting the crack. This occurs principally in high volume fraction regions found in the sized glass/polyester specimens, where the fibre does not disperse well but remains in small bundles (Fig.23). Fibre debonding appears dark, due to internal reflection at the newly created interface. In lower volume fraction regions, particularly in the unsized, dispersed glass fibre systems, there is again a tendency for single fibres to arrest a crack, and the crack appears to be temporarily diverted either side of the fibre. This behaviour is predicted by Grief and Sanders (9) who calculate the stress concentration at a crack tip to drop to zero as the crack approaches a fibre. At first the crack appears to propagate around the fibre

without any debonding at the fibre/matrix interface. Without having a strain discontinuity, there must be a layer of matrix around the fibre, so that the fibre is locally constraining the matrix (Fig. 24). However, the crack will intercept the fibre, and some debonding occurs at the interface. The two diverted forks of the crack eventually unite on the far side of the fibre, but have usually grown out of the original plane, so a step is formed which can be seen on the fracture surface (Fig. 25). The interaction of cracks with single fibres is at present being studied in greater detail.

Matrix failure is frequently observed, although rarely away from the fibres. Matrix cracks are common at any form of stress concentrator, such as fibre ends, fibre crossover points, fibre breaks and fibres in close proximity. This type of cracking is the most commonly observed event in glass fibre reinforced PMMA model specimens, and every fibre within fifty fibre diameters of the crack tip develops matrix cracks at the fibre ends (Fig. 26). This shows that, in locally highly strained regions such as just ahead of the crack, the easiest sites for crack initiation are fibre ends and fibre crossovers, due to their stress concentrating effect on the matrix adjacent to the fibres. Photoelastic information is also available (10,11) which points to the importance of stress concentrators, such as fibre ends and breaks, where the high interfacial shear stress combines with high tensile stresses to produce severe stress concentrations. Matrix cracks are also observed in the model systems at fibre breaks, another source of stress concentration (Fig. 27).

Fracture theories for fibre reinforced plastics are generally based on fibre fracture in some form. Parratt (12) suggests that fracture in a composite occurs as a result of random sized fractures when the fibres have been shortened to the extent that they are unable to carry the applied stress. Then failure occurs by shear of the matrix or at the fibre/matrix interface. Rosen (13) implies that breakdown occurs due to the accumulation of breaks in a local region of the composite. Failure then occurs when a large number of breaks form in one region, and the load applied cannot be transferred across some plane perpendicular to the load direction. Both of these theories are based on fibre fracture, and involve considerable fibre fracture, at least in a localised region around the fracture. Experimental evidence has shown that very little, if any, fibre fracture occurs in reinforced thermoplastics during fracture. Fibre length distributions have been measured before and after testing, the latter distribution being determined from a sample next to the fracture surface, and no fibre fracture can be detected. This implies that fracture is matrix controlled rather than fibre controlled. Evidence from the model systems suggests that failure is initiated in the matrix adjacent to fibres, by the stress concentrating effects of fibre ends, breaks and crossovers. Sections through thermoplastic specimens show very little fibre fracture, but considerable matrix cracking, particularly around fibres, especially fibre ends and interfaces. Cracks are observed

both near the fracture surface, and up to some considerable distance away (Fig. 13).

It is useful to explain the observed relationship between fracture strain and fibre volume fraction in terms of this fracture mechanism. Fracture strains in reinforced thermoplastics show a rapid decrease with increased fibre volume fraction, and then level off to a nearly constant value, which is below the fibre failure strain (1, 3, 4, 5). To explain this, the existence of a region of modified matrix around the fibres is postulated, which strains only to the same extent as the fibres. There is much evidence for this, in that the values of fibre/matrix bond strength determined from SEM studies and from a theoretical equation (1, 3, 4, 5) derived in this Department, exceed the matrix shear yield stress by a factor of three in the carbon/nylon system, and by one and a half times in the glass/nylon system. Bessell, Hull and Shortall (14) have made microscopic studies on fibre reinforced thermoplastics, and show that the spherulite structure is altered adjacent to fibre surfaces possibly due to preferential nucleation at the fibre.

Tests on the model systems have shown that cracks tend to propagate around fibres at first, leaving a layer of matrix around the fibre intact (see earlier discussion). This again suggests that matrix adjacent to the fibre is modified in some way. In crystalline polymers this is almost certainly a modification of the spherulite structure whilst in amorphous polymers it could be a variation of molecular structure.

At high volume fractions, the fibre-modified-matrix regions will overlap to form a continuous network, so that failure will then occur when the strain in these regions reaches the point at which cracks are initiated at stress concentrations at fibre ends, breaks and crossovers. In this case the macroscopic strain is uniform throughout the composite, since the modified matrix forms a continuous network, but the composite failure strain will be below the fibre failure strain, on account of the stress concentrating effects.

At low V_f , the modified matrix does not overlap, allowing rearrangement of locally high stresses by local matrix deformation (observed in low V_f specimens in SEM work), so reducing the effect of stress concentrations. This also means that since the unmodified matrix can strain more than the fibre, a higher composite strain is required before stress concentrators are raised to the level where they initiate cracks. In this case, the strains in the matrix, fibre, and composite overall, are not equal, and thus any relationship based on a linear law of mixtures is not applicable. A possible alternative relationship might be of the form:-

$$\frac{l}{\epsilon_c} = \frac{V_f}{\epsilon_f} + \frac{V_m}{\epsilon_m} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

This is of similar form to equations used to describe other properties (e.g. thermal conductivity) in two phase systems, where the components are parallel to the test direction. The equation also fits the two boundary conditions:-

$$\text{at } V_f = 0 \quad \epsilon_c^u = \epsilon_m^u$$

$$\text{at } V_f = 1 \quad \epsilon_c^u = \epsilon_f^u$$

A constant C may be incorporated into this equation to take into account the off-axis effects of the fibres, and variation of the value of ϵ_f^u from the fibre failure strain due to stress concentration. Another constant is needed to account for the modified matrix, since the effective V_f is enhanced by this matrix, and the fibre plus modified matrix should be treated together. The effective volume fraction, that of the fibre and modified matrix is V_{fm} , and is given by:-

$$V_{fm} = \beta V_f \quad \text{where } \beta = \frac{R^2}{r^2}$$

and R is the radius of the modified matrix sheath around the fibre. Substituting into equation (4) this gives:

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon_c^u} = \frac{C \beta V_f}{\epsilon_f^u} + \frac{(1 - \beta) V_f}{\epsilon_m^u} \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

thus, $\frac{1}{\epsilon_c^u} = A V_f + B \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$

where $A = \beta \left(\frac{C}{\epsilon_f^u} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_m^u} \right)$ and $B = \frac{1}{\epsilon_m^u}$

This relationship appears to agree with experimental evidence in that $1/\epsilon_c^u$ v. V_f is linear at low values of V_f (< 0.2) and R/r appears to be of the order 1.6.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In fibre reinforced thermoplastics excellent stiffness enhancement may be achieved by the incorporation of glass or carbon fibres. Optimum properties are realised when the fibre/matrix interface is strong and the average fibre length exceeds $5 L_c$. The tensile strength enhancement is not as great as that of stiffness owing to the reduced ductility of the fibre filled materials.

At elevated temperatures both stiffness and strength are reduced to a greater extent than would be suggested by the reduction in matrix properties alone, suggesting that the fibre/matrix

bond strength is also reduced. However, the ductility remains low even at temperatures sufficient to halve the stiffness compared with ambient temperature.

The actual value of the strain at fracture is dependent on both fibre and matrix but is slightly less than the accepted fibre strain to fracture. This suggests, either, that the fibres in the composite fail at lower stresses than predicted, or, that failure is initiated in the matrix at fibre ends or intersections. The experimental work, however, provided no evidence to support the fibre failure hypothesis.

Observation of failure in model systems has revealed several mechanisms whereby matrix fracture is initiated at the fibre/matrix interface, especially at fibre ends. These observations are also supported by optical and scanning electron microscopy of the fibre reinforced thermoplastics.

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Fig. 2. UTS v. V_f

- A. "Long" carbon fibre B. "Short" carbon fibre
 C. "Long" glass fibre D. "Short" glass fibre

Fig.3. Failure Strain v. V_f

- A. 'Long' carbon fibre
- B. 'Short' carbon fibre
- C. 'Long' glass fibre
- D. 'Short' glass fibre

Fig.4. Sketch of double cantilever beam specimen

Fig. 5. Modulus v. Temperature

Fig. 6. UTS v. Temperature

Variation of mechanical properties with temperature.

A. Nylon 6.6 B. Nylon/Glass C. Nylon/Carbon D. Polypropylene E. P.P./Glass F. P.P./Carbon

Fig. 7. Fracture Strain v. Temperature

Variation of mechanical properties with temperature.

A. Nylon 6.6 B. Nylon/Glass C. Nylon/Carbon D. Polypropylene E. P.P./Glass F. P.P./Carbon

Fig. 8. Modulus v. Temperature

Fig.9. UTS v. Temperature

Fig.10. Fracture Strain v. Temperature

Variation of mechanical properties with temperature.

A. Nylon 6.6 B. Nylon/Glass C. Nylon/Carbon D. Polypropylene E. P.P./Glass F. P.P./Carbon

Fig.11. Stress v. Strain 20°C

Fig.12. Stress v. Strain 50°C

Fig.13. Section of F RTP

Fig.14. Nylon/Glass 20°C x 159

Fig.15. Nylon/Carbon -40°C x 240

Fig.16. Nylon/Carbon 60°C x 600

Fig.17. PP/Carbon 20°C x 1.2K

Fig.18. PP/Glass -70°C x 700

Fig.19. Nylon/Glass -50°C x 1.3K

Fig.20. Nylon/Carbon 60°C x 1.2K

Fig.21. Nylon(wet)/Carbon 20°C x 1.35K

Fig.22. Fibre pull-out

Fig.23. Crack blunting by fibre debonding

Fig.24. Crack growth around a fibre

Fig.25. Matrix step by a fibre

Fig.26. Cracks at fibre ends in PMMA.

Fig.27. Crack at fibre break.